

Separation, Anti-Separation and U Ba Galay's Cartoons

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Abstract

The art of cartoon occurred simultaneously with the journals and magazines in the world of journalism in Myanmar. The cartoons which were produced in 1915 were drawn by Shwe Talay (a) Cartoonist Saya U Ba Galay. After annexation of the whole of Myanmar the British Imperialists brought the administration of Myanmar under Indian Government and made Myanmar as one of the States of India. The whole Myanmar nationals wanted to be free from British Colonialism. But some people wanted to stay in unity with India, for the lime being because they considered, simply, the way how to combat which they thought the extremely powerful Government, who would lead, in which way to due to gain Independence and thought that would it be sooner to gain Independence by struggling hand in hand with the Indian Congress, and the Imperialist may be scared by their struggle in anti-separation with India, and they would struggle hand in hand with India before gaining the administration which they liked, and struggle together with India and would not separation but stay together. Many Newspapers and Journals described about that separation and anti-separation problem. The great Cartoonist U Ba Galay who took part much in that event. U Ba Galay had illustrated that though the Myanmar peoples had disintegrated anti-separation at last the British had managed to do for their interest.

Key Wards, Ba Galay, Cartoons, Separation, Anti Separation.

Introduction

In Study of history it is made by various designs such as chronicle study of the events, Selecting and in study of the significant movements, and spot study of the prominent organizations and their leaders and deep differentiate of their problems. This is a paper to illustrate the Myanmar complicated political problem from the point of view of a cartoonist which he had drawn and presented. No political problem of a state is ever straight and simple especially there used to raise problems in transition from one era to another, from one administrative system to another. One cannot over come such problems in study of history. When the problem of separation and anti-separation for Myanmar which was ruled together with India. When attempts were made to separation Myanmar which was ruled together with India, the problem of separation and anti-separation arose up. This was the most prominent problem in the prewar history of Myanmar.

The art of cartoon occurred simultaneously with the journals and magazines in the world of journalism in Myanmar. The cartoons which were produced in 1915 were drawn by Shwe Talay (a) Cartoonist Saya U Ba Galay.¹ The cartoonist U Ba Galay was born of his father U Pho Thin and Mother Daw Thae Hmoim in Pathein. U Ba Galay was a Muslim and expired in Hinthada on 5th June 1945. As U Ba Galay had not only recorded the Myanmar

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political problem in his Cartoons but also had created a happy go lucky old man in the name of U Shwe Yoe in Myanmar movie and dramatic life.(Ludu Daw Ahmar, *Shwe Yoe*, Mandalay, Kyeepwayei Press, 1969, P12, hereafter cited as Daw Ahmar, Shwe Yoe.) When efforts were made to find out and collect U Ba Galay's cartoons for this paper on separation and anti-separation problems expressed by U Ba Galays' Cartoons to refer to in the eighteen cartoons related to the matter were found and eight of those cartoons would be extracted and presented with.

After annexation of the whole of Myanmar the British Imperialists brought the administration of Myanmar under Indian Government and made Myanmar as one of the States of India. Therefore Myanmar had become a state under the Governor General of India. After such administration the British came to realize that it would be more beneficial for them by separation Myanmar from India and governed separately, when it came into 20th Century, by calculation of various aspects of political, economics affairs etc. (Furnivall J.S, Burma past and present (far eastern survey), Americas Institute of Pacific Relations 25 Feb 1958. P53). Therefore preparations were made to separation Myanmar from India.

In such preparation the cunning colonialists had exercised the dual interest method. The first interest was to mislead Myanmar that they had favoured the Myanmar's desire to separation from India and to be a democratic act and the second one was to split the momentum of struggle by the Myanmar who had begun to wake up with political views.

The whole Myanmar nationals wanted to be free from British Colonialism. But some people wanted to stay in unity with India, for the lime being because they considered, simply, the way how to combat which they thought the extremely powerful Government, who would lead, in which way to due to gain Independence and thought that would it be sooner to gain Independence by struggling hand in hand with the Indian Congress, and the Imperialist may be scared by their struggle in anti-separation with India, and they would struggle hand in hand with India before gaining the administration which they liked, and struggle together with India and would not separation but stay together. (Than Tun, A modern History of Myanmar, 1752 - 1948 – Yangon – Loka Ahlin Publishing house, August 2010 – P145) That view may be the idea of high impression and relying on the leadership of Mahattama Gandhi and followers and the ideas to take refuge under the shade of the Congress Party. Those who were in favour of separation had realized the grievances suffered by Myanmar by staying in unity with India and sincerely thought that if was better to get separated and struggle independently to have liberated. (Cady John, F. History of Modern Burma, New York, Collnel University Press, 1958. p. 283). Therefore the case of separation and anti-separation was the problem in which the Myanmar nationals had diversity of view among them and wasted time and energy. Many Newspapers and Journals described about that separation and anti-separation problem. The great Cartoonist U Ba Galay who took part much in that event.

It was long time ago that Myanmar people had demanded for separation of Myanmar out of India. Even in the vol 1 no.1 of the Myanmar earliest Magazine, Myanmar Alin, there was an article demanding for Separation. Demand was made by the heading of "***Separation of Burma from India***". (Myanmar Alin Magazine, Vol. 1, No.1, January 1912. p.32)

The Myanmar Alin Magazine described the matter as follows –

Myanmar was suffering seriously by administration of it as a state of India. Therefore please get separated and govern it. Myanmar is not similar to any other state in India, In relating to revenue it is a state which could be collected many times higher amount than any other state in India. The revenue could be collected thirty times of Bombay region, ten times more than Madras region,

and five times more than Bengal region. Internal revenue is also the same. Myanmar is paying rupees three cores and seven and a half million annually. There are many states in India where food is insufficient and population is starving. To feed them with the revenue from Burma is very painful. For Burma needs much funds to be used for her development. The pioneer English Newspaper, published in India stated that Indian Government had to spend much money in war expenditure during the war of occupation of Burma and there were also ample amount of expenditure of suppress the insurgents as Burma was not stabilized for some time and Burma should have repay those expenditure. There is no custom of in the world to repay the expenditure occurred in aggression and occupation of one's country. In reality Burma was occupied easily. Burma is not similar in race, religion and belief with India and moreover the Bay of Bengal is dividing them apart. And when the border problem arises with Chinese in the northwest of Burma, the British Government would not be able to get the information promptly and would have to get information through Indian Government. If the king George V was able to transfer the Indian Capital from Calcutta to Delhi he should have been able to separate Burma from India make a crown Colony as the state of in Ceylon ruled directly from England. It is stated to send a reasonable person and rule it.

The fifth YMBA congress held in Pinyinmana on 1 October 1917 has laid down a resolution on 4 October. The resolution was for separation of Myanmar out of India and to grant rule similar to that of India. Then the Secretary Montagu came to India in a mission with U Ba Pe, U May Aung and Mandalay U Su and U Pho Tha, U Thinn and U Ba Tu as the representatives of the Myanmar Mercantile and Co operative Unions to submit and demand those resolutions. (Lay Maung, U. *History of Myanmar Politics, People manual series, BTS, Yangon. Vol.1, 1973 Pg 169-171.*) The Thuria Magazine, the voice of YMBA at that time also wrote and made demands on its head limes for separation of Burma from India under the Heading of "The India and Burma". (Thuria Megazine, December, 1917)

In the same Magazine U Ba Galay had drawn two Cartoons about separation. Those two Cartoons were the one drawn for the first time by U Ba Galay. The following captions were illustrated under the Cartoon drawings.

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When the Myanmar found out that India is to be granted with better Administration system and Myanmar was not included in that programme in the Montague Chan sport report, the Myanmar people never so bitterly suffered on the British Government. It was more realized that it is essential to separation Myanmar from India. (Report of the Indian Statutory

Commission, vol. II, Calcutta, Government of India.)Therefore U Ba Galay has drawn a Cartoon with the caption that – The baby who a cry is fed with milk.

When the Myanmar future administration was discussed in England the potentials for granting Burma the type of administration wider than Diarchy system were learnt. Therefore with the hope that there would have more opportunities and power when the new administration system in granted it is learnt that some of the leaders on anti-separation side persuaded prearranged to go in hands with them and divide the power between them. Members of the 21 group decided and traveled to various part of Myanmar when they arrived back and relayed the news about the discussions in England and at the some time propagated the separation speeches. Those newspapers that supported the separation also persuaded with various articles and cartoons. Cartoon U Ba Galay also published a Cartoon with the following Caption in the Thuria Daily. (Thuria Newspaper, 15 May 1932)

More over it was illustrated as a humorous cartoon not only the politicians but also ordinary peoples various obsessions on the separation and anti-separation affairs. (Myanmar Alin Newspaper, 25 June 1932)

The following Cartoon was drawn on the events of the politicians to contend in the election for the purpose of separation and anti-separation. (Thuria Journal, 6 November 1932)

It was a cartoon to place a voter on his head in pre election time and place the voter under his feet and step on him after he was elected as a member of parliament.

U Ba Galay did not draw his cartoons only on the separation side but also drew cartoons for the anti-separation side. U Ba Galay had illustrated the creation of U Ba Phe group, the 21 group (the group who favour separation) to pose as majority though they were minority. (Bandoola Journal, 7 December 1932)

As the British Government looked forward for their Capitalists interests and interest of their Empire did not lay emphasis on Myanmar desire. As they had realized that it would serve their interest if they grant Myanmar desire 20 years after their demand they had separated Burma from India on 1st May 1937. Therefore U Ba Galay had drawn this Cartoon on the full page of the Thuria Newspaper. (Thuria Newspaper, 5 April 1937)

The British did not question or consider anything when they wanted to be separated. It meant that the British Judge John Bull had heard one side only and handed down the Separation order.

In conclusion it could be said that it was the early stage of Capitalist democracy. At that time the problem of separation and anti-separation served for the interest of the British. The population in a village was divided into separation and anti-separation sides of northern

part and southern part of the village and became enemy among them. The Abbot of the Eastern Monastery and Abbot of western Monastery did not have their alms food together. There were disagreements among families and quarreled between brothers and sisters, husband and wife, the diversity of views spread to towns and rural areas and lost the goal to fight against the Imperialists. U Ba Galay had illustrated that though the Myanmar peoples had disintegrated anti-separation at last the British had managed to do for their interest.

Acknowledgement

I hereby express my deep gratitude towards Professor Dr. Kyaw Win (Secretary, Myanmar Historic commission). Special Thanks to Dr Min Aung (Rector-Bago University), Pro-Rector Dr Yin Yin Than, Dr Su Su Myaine (Professor Head), Dr Myint Myint Khaing (Professor), Associate Professors, Lecturers, Assistant Lecturers and Tutors. Especially my parents who gave smith to me and my older brother Ko Myo Thura and younger brother Ko Wai Phyo Ko Ko for every assistance provided to enable my favorites research works enthusiastically.

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